

ASSESSMENT OF PEARL MILLET MARKETING IN MAKURDI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study assessed pearl millet marketing in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study include: to describe the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, evaluate the market structure and performance of millet in the study area, estimate the profitability of pearl millet marketing in the study area; ascertain the determinants of wholesale and retail selling prices of pearl millet., and identify the constraints to millets marketing in the study area. Purposively, four major millet markets were selected within the State and a total of 120 respondents were considered at random for the study. The Results of descriptive statistics showed that more females (65%) invested in millet marketing than males (35%) indicating that millet marketing is majorly a female dominated enterprise in the study area. The mean age of the respondents was 45 years and mean household size of 10 persons. The mean monthly income from millet marketing in the study area was ₦275, 000, an indication that millet marketing is a profitable enterprise in the study area. The Gini coefficient for wholesale millet marketers was computed to be 0.315, while that of retail sale was 0.304 indicating high level of competition among millet marketers in the study area. The results of regression estimates indicated that quantity of millet purchased (0.040), and purchase price (0.269) were the significant determinants of wholesale selling price of millet while the quantity of millet purchased (0.243), Purchase price (0.531) and transportation cost (0.273) were the significant determinants of retail selling price of pearl millet. Findings revealed that insecurity ($\bar{x} = 4.28$), high transportation cost ($\bar{x} = 4.28$), middlemen instruction ($\bar{x} = 4.26$), poor market information ($\bar{x} = 4.01$), poor prices ($\bar{x} = 3.81$) and inadequate credit facilities ($\bar{x} = 3.70$) were the major problems facing the supply chain actors in the business. The study recommends formation of group cooperative to minimize the high cost of transportation and enhance profit margin among millet suppliers. More importantly, there is need for conflict resolution among farmers and herders to forestall peace and order for increased food production (including pearl millet) as this will stimulate economic growth and poverty reduction in the country.

Keywords: Marketing Margin, Transaction Cost, Pearl Millet, Benue State, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pearl millet is an important cereal that makes up about two- third of the total cereal production in Africa (FAO, 2008). It is a major staple diet to millions of the poor in the drier regions of Nigeria and a crucial resource to the small-scale farmers as well as those making it available in the markets. The crop is favored due to its productivity and short growing season under dry, high temperature conditions. Market access plays an essential task in assuring better income and welfare to marketing actors; despite the fact that well-organized marketing system is a key requirement, many described it as informal and poorly developed in most developing countries (Mlozi *et al.*, 2003). Supply chain actors play vital role in bridging agricultural produce, whether the markets are highly sophisticated or periodic markets with extremely limited infrastructure, such as agricultural markets in Nigeria, or elsewhere in the developing world.

Regardless of the multitude of such actors' animation that range from small farmers in rural markets to large traders operating in structured networks, and regional trade, amid increasing transaction cost; such markets still strives with poor quality grains, imperfect competition and high transaction cost (Abay, 2010). Marketing involves all processes in the movement of products that consumers need from the point of production to the point of purchase. Marketing is concerned with all stages of operation which facilitate the movement of commodities from the farm to the consumers (Isibor *et al.*, 2021). Marketing has economic value because it gives form, time and place utility (Matuschke and Qaim, 2019). Efficient marketing plays a crucial role in an economy (Isibor *et al.*, 2021). Agricultural marketing is a form of marketing that includes all goods and services related to agriculture. These products will absolutely or indirectly support the effort to produce and deliver agricultural products from the farm to the consumers. Millet marketing has been worse heightened by low productivity in recent years, hence meeting present and immediate future need is a big challenge.

Pearl millet grains usually reach the markets from outlying surplus production areas through suppliers such as rural collectors, farmers, or search agents. Other actors as well enable the flow, out from the markets to deficit areas in other regions of the country (Baba *et al.*, 2009). This structure implies that the bulk of pearl millet grain marketed in the country are exchanged in the rural markets, crossing relatively long distances, and is exchanged between supply chain actors and brokers who otherwise have no contact (Baba *et al.*, 2009). This has placed renewed attention on supply chain and trading practices and this study link these not only to evidence on supply actors marketing margins but also to their net margins using data on marketing operation, and transaction costs in the marketing of pearl millet in the study area. Fighting hunger and malnutrition are some of the measures which should be taken to guarantee higher income and better living conditions for the most vulnerable communities which are mostly formed by rural women who produce millet, especially in developing countries such as Nigeria.

The broad objective of this study is to assess millet marketing in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Makurdi. Specifically, the study (i) describing the socio economic characteristics of millet sellers in the study area, (ii) evaluate the market structure and performance of millet in the study area, (iii) estimate the profitability

Difference between selling price and buying price

$$MM = SP - BP \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

MM = Marketing margin SP = Selling price

BP = Buying price:

Also, marketing margin is given as:

$$MM = \frac{\text{Selling price} - \text{purchased cost}}{\text{Selling price}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Marketing profit (per 100kg of millet)

Marketing margin less marketing cost. That is:

$$\text{Profit} = MM - MC \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:

MM = marking margin

MC = Marketing cost (cost of transportation, handling, shop rent etc.)

$$\text{Rate of return} = \frac{(MM - MC) 100}{BP + MC} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Mark-up analysis

$$\text{Mark-up} = \frac{(SP - BP) 100}{SP} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Operational efficiency (OE) analysis

$$OE_i = \frac{\text{Sales}}{MC} (\text{Local efficiency}) \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

$$OE = \frac{OE_i}{OE_o} \times 100 (\text{Global efficiency}) \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

OE_o = Most locally efficient firm.

The regression model

The model was implicitly expressed as follows:

$$Q_i = f (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, \epsilon_i) \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

The explicit forms of the model were expressed as follows:

Linear Function

$$Y = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + b_5 X_5 + b_6 X_6 + b_7 X_7 + b_8 X_8 \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

Where:

Q_i =Quantity of millet sold (Kg) X_1 =Price per unit sold (Naira) X_2 =Price of other substitutes (Naira) X_3 =Cost of transportation (Naira)

X_4 =Equipment cost of marketing (Naira) X_5 =Age of household head (years) X_6 =Educational level of household head (years) X_7 =Sex (male=0, female=1)

X_8 =Marital status (married=0, single=1)

U =Stochastic term b_0 =constant

B_1 - b_{10} =regression coefficients.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of Millet Farmers in the Study Area

Socio-economic characteristics of millet marketers is presented in **Table 1**. The Results of descriptive statistics showed that more females invested in millet marketing than males. Specifically, 65 percent of the total respondents were females while 35 percent of the respondents are male. This is an indication that millet marketing is majorly a female dominated enterprise in the study area. The majority (52.5%) of the millet marketers were married while only 33.3 percent were still single with average age of 45 years and mean household size of 10 persons. The average household size of 10 persons estimated in the study is higher than the recommended national average of 6 persons per household (NBS, 2020). This implies that the more the household size increases, the more the quest to generate money to take care of the home through marketing of millet in the study area. However, the large household size has implications on food security of the households. According to Ogebe *et al.* (2019), an increase in household size would increase the coping strategy index, meaning that increase in household size in general increases the food insecurity of the household. This is because large household size could constitute a serious hindrance in the face of sickness, educational funding, feeding and other activities that compete for the meagre resources of the households.

The findings revealed that millet marketing is more attractive to married people, since it improves income, maximize resource use efficiency and also ensure their household's welfare and well-being. More so, the mean age of 45 years implies that millet marketers in the study area are still in their productive age and are capable of deploying their energy into productive and useful ventures. Majority (40.0%) of the sampled respondents had secondary with average marketing experiences of 10 years which is supposed to enhance their marketing performance and efficiency. This is because of the assertion that the longer the years of experience the better marketing performance of traders. The mean monthly income from millet marketing in the study area was ₦275,000. This is an indication that millet marketing is a profitable and farmers who cultivate this crop can be encouraged to channel their efforts and resources more into its production so as to enhance larger volume of marketing activities.

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of Peal Millet Marketers in the Study Area (n=120)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative (%)
Sex			
Male	42	35.0	35.0
Female	78	65.0	100.0
Age (years)			
20-30	36	30.0	30.0
31-40	60	50.0	80.0
41-50	13	10.8	90.8
51-60	7	5.8	96.6
>60	4	3.4	100.0
Marital status			
Single	40	33.3	33.3
Married	63	52.5	85.8
Divorced	6	5.0	90.8
Widowed/widower	11	9.2	100.0
Household size (number)			
1-2	31	25.8	25.8
3-5	58	48.3	74.1
6-10	25	20.8	94.9
>10	6	5.0	100.0
Educational level			
Primary	48	40.0	40.0
Secondary	68	56.7	96.7
Tertiary	2	1.7	98.4
No formal education	2	1.7	100.0
Marketing experience (years)			
1-2	15	12.5	12.5
3-5	43	35.8	48.3
6-10	36	30.0	78.3
11-15	18	15.0	93.3
>15	8	6.7	100.0
Monthly income (₦)			
50,000-100,000	17	14.2	14.2
100,001-200,000	57	47.5	61.7
200,001-300,000	39	32.5	94.2
300,001-400,000	5	4.2	98.4
400,001-500,000	2	1.7	100.0
Mean = 275,000			

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

Supply margin, Marketing margin and Marketing cost of Pearl Millet

The total marketing margin is the difference between what the consumers pays and what the wholesaler/retailer

receives for his millet, in other words, it is the difference between selling price and buying price. For convenience and to reflect the market practice in the area, the marketing profit as determined from the analysis is based on 100kg bag of millet and was considered in the calculations.

The findings revealed that despite the highest marketing margin incurred by the wholesalers in supplying and marketing of millet in the study area; they also incur the highest profit margin (35.23%). Retailers got the lowest profit margin as well as the lowest cost of marketing in the business (₦7180.8). This was due to the forgone alternative cost associated with search and transportation. From the analysis, profit from the millet business in the study area was estimated by subtracting the marketing cost (MC) from the marketing margin (MM). The result shows that the profit realized by the wholesalers was ₦ 3,599.6, while that of the retailers was estimated at ₦ 2,939.7 This indicates that supply and marketing of pearl millet was profitable enterprise in the study areas with percentage of rate of returns per Naira invested for the wholesalers and retailers estimated at 27 % and 21%, respectively.

Table 2: Supply margin, Marketing margin and Marketing cost of Pearl millet

Cost Items	Cost Prices ₦/100Kg bag	and*Gross Marketing margin	Supply/** Marketing cost	Total Supply/***	Profit Margins (₦/100Kg As % of	
					Amount	As % of cost price
Wholesaler						
Average buying price	8874.3	8076.4	4476.8	3599.6	35.23	
Total Supply/Marketing cost	4476.8					
Cost prices	10218.2					
Average selling price	16950.7					
Rate of return	0.27					
Retailer						
Average buying price	9568.8	7180.8	4240.3	2939.7	26.85	
Total Supply/Marketing cost	4240.3					
Cost prices	10950.4					
Average selling price	16749.6					
Rate of return	0.21					

*Gross marketing margin (value added) =Average selling price –Average buying price. **Average selling and /buying price at different level were based on the own survey of this study, 2024. ***The time dimension for profit margin is one year (2024).

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024.

Market Structure of the Pearl Millet Marketers in the Study Area

The Gini coefficient was used to determine the structure of the market for millet. The results of Gini coefficient (Table 3) showed Gini Coefficient (GC) values of 0.315 and 0.304 for wholesalers and retailers, respectively. These values are closer to zero and hence indicate high level of competition among millet marketers in the study area.

Table 3: Results of Gini-coefficient for Retail and Wholesale Pearl Millet Marketing

Variable	Retailers				Wholesalers			
	Freq.	%	Cum.	XY	Freq.	%	Cum.	XY
Income (₦'000,000)								
100000-2000000	9	0.15	0.15	0.0225	10	0.167	0.167	0.0279
20000001-4000000	31	0.517	0.667	0.3448	32	0.533	0.700	0.3731
40000001-6000000	19	0.317	0.984	0.3119	14	0.233	0.933	0.2174
60000001-8000000	1	0.017	1.00	0.0170	4	0.067	1.00	0.0670
Total	60			0.6962	60			0.6854

$\sum XY$ (Retailer) = 0.6962; GC (Retailer) = 1- 0.6930 = **0.3038**

$\sum XY$ (wholesaler) = 0.6854; GC (Wholesaler) = 1-0.6854 = **0.3146** Source: Author's Computation, 2024.

Pricing Efficiency of Millet in the Study Area

Table 4 showed the results of millet market pricing efficiency in the study area. The retail average selling price of millet per 100kg was ₦16749.60 while its cost per 100kg was estimated at ₦10950.40 and the pricing efficiency ratio was calculated to be > 1 (1.53). Therefore, it could be concluded that retail millet marketing price was under efficient as the marketers are running business at a loss. In respect to wholesale price efficiency, the average wholesale selling price per 100kg was ₦15950.70 and it cost per 100kg was ₦10218.20. The pricing efficiency ratio was found to be > 1 (1.66) which implies that wholesale pearl millet marketing price was also under efficient. The non-significant t-test value of 0.598 for wholesalers and -0.990 for retailers indicates that there is no difference between marketing margin and marketing cost at both wholesale and retail levels. This implies the existence of pricing efficiency in millet marketing in the study area, meaning prices at both wholesale and retail marketing reflect cost of marketing and that millet marketers behaviors in the area are not exploitative.

Table 4: Results of Pricing Efficiency Analysis of Millet Marketers in the Study Area

Variables	Wholesalers				Retailers			
	Mean	S.E	T-value	Sig.	Mean	S.E	T-value	Sig.
Marketing margin (MM)	8076.4	200.6	0.598 ^{NS}	0.555	7180.8	100.09	-0.990 ^{NS}	0.326
Marketing cost (MC)	4476.8	49.407			4240.3	48.497		
Average selling price (SP)	16950.7				16749.6			
Average cost price (CP)	10218.2				10950.4			
Pricing efficiency ratio	1.66				1.53			

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Note: NS = Not significant

Mark-up Analysis

Markup is the percentage added to the cost of goods to obtain selling price. The result in Table 5 showed that the mark-up price for wholesalers and retailers were estimated at 21.24% and 17.56% respectively, which is a sign of reasonable pricing of millet in the area, in view of the fact that supply is coming from far places.

Table 5: Results of Mark-up Analysis of Marketers in the Study Area

Parameters	Computational procedure	Values (%)
Markup value for wholesalers $SP - BP - MC$ $= \frac{\quad}{SP} \times 100$	$\frac{16950.7 - 8874.3 - 4476.8}{16950.7} \times 100$ $= \frac{16749.6 - 9568.8 - 4240.3}{16749.6} \times 100$	21.24
Markup value for retailers $= SP - BP - MC$ $X100$ SP	16749.6	17.56

Source: Author's Computation, 2024.

Operational Efficiency of Pearl Millet Marketing in the Study Area

The result of operational efficiency of wholesalers and retailers is presented in Table 6. The result of analysis showed that 20.0% of the wholesale millet markets are within operational efficiency of 70 to 80, with 63.3% operated within 81 to 90, while those in the efficiency range of between 91 and 100 accounted for 16.7%. It is equally noted from the analysis that the operational efficiency of the retailers within the same categories of the wholesalers accounted for 1.7%, 73.3% and 25.0%, respectively.

Majority of both wholesalers and retailers falls within the efficiency range of 81-90%. In comparing the efficiencies of the wholesalers and retailers, the retailers showed higher operational efficiency than wholesalers, except at range 70-80 where wholesalers had 20.0% as against 1.7% for retailers. Overall, both wholesaling and retailing functions are operationally efficient. This means that these functions of marketing were performed at the lowest costs possible in the study area.

Table 6: Results of Operational Efficiency Analysis of Millet Market in the Study Area

Range (%)	Frequency		Percentage	
	Wholesalers	Retailers	Wholesalers	Retailers
70-80	12	1	20.0	1.7
81-90	38	44	63.3	73.3
91-100	10	15	16.7	25.0

Source: Author's Computation, 2024.

Determinants of Selling Prices in Wholesale and Retail Marketing of Pearl Millet

The study employed the Cobb-Douglas function to ascertain the determinant of selling prices in wholesale and retail millet marketing. The estimated R² of the model was 0.73 implying that 73% of the variations in wholesale

selling prices were explained by the independent variables included in the model. The F-statistic (6.322) confirms the suitability of the overall regression equation. The result (**Table 7a**) indicated that quantity of millet purchased by wholesalers was negatively related to wholesale selling price and was statistically significant at ($P > 0.05$) while purchase price and was found to be positively related to wholesale selling price and this was significant at ($P > 0.01$) implying that the higher the quantity of millet purchased by wholesalers, the lesser are their selling prices and this might be attributed to the fact that bulk buying attracts discounts which invariably reduce cost per unit and therefore give the sellers the opportunity at selling at reduced price consequently, facilitating high rate of turnover and more profit.

On determinants of retail selling price (**Table 7b**), the analysis revealed that transportation cost, quantity purchased by retailers and purchase price were major determinants in retail millet marketing and were statistically significant. However, the quantity purchased (X_1) showed a negative relationship but was statistically significant ($P = 0.01$). This showed that the higher the marketing factor i.e. transportation cost, purchase price and storage cost the higher will be the retail selling price of pearl millet while the higher the quantity purchased by the retailer, the lesser its selling price with respect to reduction in price paid to wholesalers.

Table 7a: Determinants of Wholesale Selling Price of Pearl Millet in the Study Area

Variables	Coefficients	T- values
β_0 (Constant)	4.095***	8.137
X_1 (Quantity purchased)	0.040**	-2.103
X_2 (Purchase price)	0.269*	3.395
X_3 (Transportation cost)	0.026	1.438
X_4 (Storage cost)	0.014	0.129
R^2	0.73	
Adjusted R^2	0.72	
F- value	6.332**	

***= Significant at 1%, **= Significant at 5%; and *= Significant at 10%

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024.

Table 7b: Determinants of Retail Selling Price of Pearl Millet in the Study Area

Variables	Coefficients	T- values
β_0 (Constant)	2.140**	2.268
X_1 (Quantity purchased)	0.243***	-3.369
X_2 (Purchase price)	0.531***	3.541
X_3 (Transportation cost)	0.273**	4.344
X_4 (Storage cost)	0.028	2.419
R^2	0.68	
Adjusted R^2	0.62	
F- value	16.961***	

***= Significant at 1%, **= Significant at 5%; and *= Significant at 10%

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024.

Perceived Challenges to Millet Marketing in the Study area

The result 4-point-liket scale showed that the problem of insecurity and high cost of transportation ($\bar{x} = 4.28$) separately, ranked first. Findings showed that the incessant farmers/herders crisis displaced millet farmers from their farming communities consequently affecting millet production and unavailability of millet thus prompting shortage in supply of product and hence high market prices. Other major problems include middlemen intrusion ($\bar{x} = 4.26$) and poor market information ($\bar{x} = 4.01$) among others. However, lack of standard measurement, pest infestation, processing and assembling and natural hazards were also perceived challenges in millet marketing but were not considered major challenges.

Table 8: Perceived Challenges in Millet Marketing in the Study area (n =120)

Challenges	Weighted sum	Weighted mean	Rank	Remark
Middlemen/ intermediaries	511	4.26	3rd	PC
Natural disaster (flood, drought)	156	1.30	10th	NC
Inadequate credit facility	444	3.70	6th	PC
Poor market information	481	4.01	4th	PC
Processing and assembling	168	1.40	9th	NC
Insecurity problem	513	4.28	1st	PC
High cost of transportation	514	4.28	1st	PC
Poor prices	457	3.81	5th	PC
Pest infestation	284	2.37	8th	NC
Lack of standard measurement	290	2.41	7th	NC

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024 **Note:** Challenges with Mean score ≥ 2.50 are considered more serious, PC= Perceived Challenge NC= Not a Challenge.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study found that the market structure of the millet in the study area is homogenous, with a well-defined conduct and performance. The study revealed that millet marketing is a profitable venture and despite the wide profit margin by the wholesalers they incurred the highest marketing cost compared to retailers. The cost associated with searching, transfer of grains from one point of purchase to another selling point constitutes the highest transaction cost associated with pearl millet supply. Insecurity, high transportation cost, middlemen instruction, poor market information, poor prices and inadequate credit facilities were the major problems facing the supply chain actors in the business. The study recommends formation of group cooperative to minimize the high cost of transportation and enhance profit margin among millet suppliers. More importantly, there is need for conflict resolution among farmers and herders to forestall peace and order for increased food production (including pearl millet) as this will stimulate economic growth and poverty reduction in the country.

Authors' Contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Author OOF designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors OGA and BPA managed the analyses of the study. Author OGA managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have not declared any conflict of interest.

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